

Partisan Winds: Group-level Polarization and Issue-framing Propel Attitudes about Local Wind Farms

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Political polarization is an obstacle to public support and effective communication for renewable energy projects. Depolarizing messages can be helpful, but it is difficult to determine where to concentrate efforts until social scientists first disentangle the effects of unconscious issue-based and conscious group norm-based polarization processes. This study investigates the extent to which attitudes toward wind energy development are polarized in the United States, focusing on attitudes about local wind farms. We tested different frames in a survey with 1,300 U.S. participants, combining implicit and explicit attitude measures to measure unconscious and conscious attitudes toward nearby wind farms, respectively. Our findings suggest that explicit attitudes toward wind farms are more polarized than implicit attitudes, emphasizing the role of conscious processes in shaping attitudes. Furthermore, perceptions of within-party support significantly influence explicit attitudes, indicating the importance of group norm-based polarization in this context. While our framing interventions aimed at addressing issue-based polarization yielded mixed results, the moderating effect of perceived within-party support underscores the potential efficacy of interventions targeting group-level processes. Regarding policy implications, our findings highlight the importance of considering both issue-based and group norm-based polarization when developing and implementing communication strategies for garnering local support for nearby renewable energy developments.

Keywords: Wind farm; Political Polarization; Framing; Local attitudes; Motivated Reasoning

1. Introduction

Climate change has become a focal point of political polarization, a phenomenon well-documented globally (Falkenberg et al., 2022; Fisher et al., 2022; Hornsey et al., 2016) and particularly pronounced in the United States (Chinn et al., 2020; Egan & Mullin, 2017, 2024). Indeed, the U.S. is the paradigmatic case where political orientation strongly predicts attitudes about climate change, with politically conservatives tending to be skeptical and liberals more inclined to believe in anthropogenic warming (Tesler, 2018). While this relationship between political orientation and climate change attitudes appears to be pervasive across various countries (Smith & Hempel, 2022), it is not as straightforward outside the U.S. due to the significant moderating influence of social and cultural factors, which render political orientation less determinant (Gregersen et al., 2020). In the US, however, the substantial impact of political polarization on public attitudes has been confirmed extensively in the literature (Egan & Mullin, 2017; Iyengar et al., 2019; McCright & Dunlap, 2011). Against this backdrop, our study focuses on a specific aspect of this polarization—attitudes toward wind farm development near residential areas in the US.

Garnering public support for the expansion of renewable energy, including wind farm development, can accelerate the energy transition (Meadowcroft, 2011). However, wind farm development is a topic of intense debate worldwide (e.g., Holowach & Parkins, 2023), with opposition intensifying as projects draw closer to residential areas (Dällenbach & Wüstenhagen, 2022; Walker et al., 2018). Moreover, in the U.S., the development and deployment of wind energy exhibits a partisan divide wherein Democrats tend to support wind farm expansion for climate change mitigation while Republicans tend to oppose it—unless there are clear economic or political benefits involved (Bessette & Mills, 2021; Gustafson et al., 2020; Jepson et al., 2012).

Within the political sphere, the underlying cause of polarization about climate change remains unclear (Druckman & McGrath, 2019), raising questions about whether it stems primarily from political ideology (i.e., an issue-based, individual-level polarization process) or partisan identification (i.e., a norm-based, group-level polarization) (Cole et al., 2023). This is because, contrary to defining political parties by ideological distinctions, most Americans identify them through group divisions (Finkel et al., 2020; Iyengar et al., 2012; Klein, 2020). Therefore, understanding the group-level processes tied to partisan identification and distinguishing them from individual-level processes related to ideology is crucial for unraveling the complexities of political polarization (Mason, 2018).

Given that political polarization impedes consensus and effective communication (Finkel et al., 2020), our study aims to contribute to disentangling the levels at which issue-based and norm-based polarization operate. As explained in the next section, we seek to investigate if issue-based polarization could be bridged when norm-based polarization is not active. By doing so, we provide insights into when framing strategies can be effective in changing attitudes and when they may backfire in a polarized society. Our findings regarding the efficacy of party-specific framings in fostering positive attitudes aim to contribute to refining communication strategies for new wind farm development in a polarized environment.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Research approach

This study explores the extent to which politically motivated reasoning and in-group social pressure contribute independently to exacerbate political polarization. Politically motivated reasoning can be defined as the tendency to align the interpretation of

information with prevailing political beliefs (Kunda, 1990; Lodge & Taber, 2000; Stanovich, 2021). In-group social pressure refers to the perceived obligation partisans feel to conform to the majority opinion within their political party. Politically motivated reasoning is triggered by an individual-level, issue-based polarization, whereas in-group social pressure is prompted by a group-level, norm-based polarization. Although politically motivated reasoning and in-group social pressure are distinct concepts, they are frequently discussed together because political issues shape individuals' alignment with political parties and, conversely, party affiliation influences their stance on political matters (Jost et al., 2022).

To disentangle the influences of issue-based and norm-based polarization, we combined an Implicit Association Test (IAT) with a traditional survey to capture implicit and explicit attitudes about wind farms, respectively. As shown in Table 1 and discussed later, we assume issue-based polarization to be measurable with the IAT and a regular questionnaire, whereas group-norm based polarization being only captured with the questionnaire. Previous research measuring polarization at the implicit level using IAT has found a division between Democrats' and Republicans' unconscious attitudes (Iyengar & Westwood, 2015), suggesting its deep-rooted nature. In contrast, explicit attitudes (i.e., conscious and intentional) have been found to be significantly more malleable and polarized than implicit attitudes (Marcos et al., 2023). Yet, the intricate interplay between unconscious and conscious polarization remains insufficiently understood because previous research has not measured both implicit and explicit attitudes towards renewable energy development to understand the nature of the underlying polarizing processes and their potential deactivation.

This study further examines whether norm-based polarization, driven consciously by awareness of in-group pressure, depends on the level of perceived within-party support.

Moreover, by controlling for perceived within-party support, this investigation addresses the existing ambiguity in the literature regarding the efficacy of framing strategies (e.g., during public engagement efforts) in reducing issue-based polarization (Rode et al., 2021; Singh & Swanson, 2017; Wolsko et al., 2016), shedding light on whether its success depends on the state of group-level processes.

In order to ease understanding throughout hypotheses formulation, Table 1 summarizes the terms related to individual and group-level polarization processes, mentioning what we assume causes these processes, their theoretical underpinning, how we plan to measure polarization and our proposed strategies to overcome it.

Psychological process	Individual-level polarization	Group-level polarization
Polarization prompted by...	Political ideology (issue-based polarization)	Partisan identification (group norm-based polarization)
Theoretically supported by...	Politically motivated reasoning	Social identity theory and self-categorization theory
Observable as...	Both implicit (unconscious) and explicit attitudes (deliberate)	Explicit attitudes only (complying with in-group social pressure requires conscious mental effort)
Measured with...	Implicit Association Test (IAT) and regular questionnaire	Regular questionnaire
Polarization addressed by...	Issue framing (tailored frame emphasizing issues relevant to each party's political ideology)	Changes in perceived within-party support (descriptive norms about what the in-group majority thinks)

Table 1. Key concepts from our research approach informing the logic of hypotheses formulation.

Despite the obvious partisan difference in the U.S. on seemingly all climate-related topics and technologies (McCright et al., 2016), we advocate that fully understanding the social acceptance of renewable energy requires a multidimensional perspective (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007) that looks beyond political partisanship or a highly simplified set of guiding objectives (Árvai & Gregory, 2021). However, in the case of this particular study, we

intentionally narrow our focus, excluding the dimensions of market acceptance (i.e., perspectives of consumers and investors) and community acceptance (i.e., considerations of justice and trust). We decided to focus on exploring the socio-political dimension of attitudes toward wind farms because socio-political acceptance is social acceptance on its broadest, most general level (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007), which makes it easier to measure. Reliably measuring market acceptance and community acceptance would divert us from the focus of our study, as this would necessitate a deeper exploration of the market adoption of wind energy and considering the particularities of each siting decision, respectively (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007).

2.1. Public reception of wind energy at the local level in the U.S.

Utility-scale wind energy has emerged as one of two primary sources of renewable electricity in the U.S.—along with large-scale solar—offering a range of advantages over fossil fuel-based power generation. These advantages include the health-benefits of mitigating climate change impacts and improving air-quality (Millstein et al., 2017), as well as economic benefits like providing a stable income stream for landowners and farmers who lease their land for wind turbine installations (Barbose et al., 2016; Mills, 2015). From 2017 to 2023, U.S. wind power grew by more than 60% to 143 GW of installed capacity (EIA, 2023), and current projections by the U.S. Energy Information Administration point to a slower but still positive trend (EIA, 2024).

However, this expansion may require deploying wind energy on a larger scale, which could potentially bring projects closer to towns and urban areas. With expansion comes the issue of local opposition, as larger renewable energy projects encounter greater opposition compared to smaller-scale projects (e.g., Nilson & Stedman, 2022). This

growing local opposition to nearby wind turbine installations is not necessarily driven by a “not-in-my-backyard” (NIMBY) response (Carley et al., 2020; Hoen et al., 2019; Rand & Hoen, 2017), but instead often results from residents’ concerns about wind’s impact on their sense of place, the rural landscape and aesthetic, and local economy including nearby property values (Batel, 2020; Brunner et al., 2023; Mills et al., 2019; Walker et al., 2018).

This shift in the way researchers think about opposition underscores the recognition that wind energy support is complex and influenced by various socio-economic and psychological factors: Risk perceptions (Baxter et al., 2013; Giordono et al., 2018), economic impacts (Bidwell, 2013; Groth & Vogt, 2014), preference for electricity generated using renewable energy (Baxter et al., 2013), proximity to protected areas (Giordono et al., 2018), and fair engagement with the locals in the planning process (Firestone, Hoen, et al., 2018; Rand & Hoen, 2017) remain key drivers of support and are often more important than visibility and pure aesthetics (Hoen et al., 2019). Understanding the importance of these factors becomes complicated because they are often intertwined with each other or used strategically by ex-local opponents to continuously delay project development (Fergen et al., 2021). Other times, residents supplant harder to quantify concerns—such as turbines’ visible impacts—with easier to quantify concerns—like noise or property values. For example, Haac et al. (2019) found that residents who did not benefit personally from nearby wind energy projects perceived the noise from the wind turbines as more annoying than it was perceived by those who did benefit.

As for the influence of political orientation on attitudes, while the political divide over local opposition to wind farms seems clearer in other countries (e.g., Walker et al., 2018), drawing conclusions for the U.S. is not as straightforward. Given the pervasive influence of political orientation on most climate-related issues in the U.S. (McCright et al., 2016),

it is intriguing that the role of political orientation in shaping attitudes towards local wind energy support remains inconclusive. While some studies suggest that members of the Republican Party and politically conservatives tend to express greater opposition to local wind farms than liberals in general (e.g., Bidwell, 2013; Carley et al., 2020), other studies only find marginal or negligible effects of political orientation (e.g., Klick & Smith, 2010), or that the percentage of former President Trump voters in a county significantly reduced contention around wind development (Bessette & Mills, 2021). One possible explanation for these mixed results is that attitudes toward nearby wind farms tend to improve over time mainly as people become more accustomed to the projects (Hoen et al., 2019). This improvement may also be caused by the provision of compensation or incentives (le Maitre et al., 2023).

2.2. Politically motivated reasoning and in-group social pressure

Given that views on climate change are significantly more polarized than attitudes toward renewable energy in the U.S. (Hazboun et al., 2020), there is a greater body of theoretical work on how political polarization exacerbates climate change views, which is pertinent to this study. In particular, the social psychology literature on political polarization regarding climate change posits that political ideology operates as an individual-level psychological process, distinct from partisan identification, which operates at the group level (Pearson et al., 2016). However, these two types of polarizing processes are not always acknowledged as distinct mechanisms (Ditto et al., 2019; Mason, 2015). This gap might be caused by the complex relationship between political ideology and partisan identification, where individuals' beliefs can shape their alignment with political parties and vice versa (Jost et al., 2022).

We adopted Pearson's (2016) theoretical approach to polarizing psychological processes because, as argued in the comprehensive literature review by Cole et al. (2023), Pearson's

(2016) terminology and theoretical framework are the most complete for distinguishing between individual-level and group-level processes. Consequently, we define individual-level, issue-based polarization as the fundamental ideological differences that exist between Democrats—who tend to favor environmental protection, progressive taxation, and government regulation—and Republicans—who tend to take the opposite stance on these issues, limiting consensus on climate-related issues (e.g., Gifford, 2011). In contrast, the term group-level, norms-based polarization is used when individuals align with specific social groups, such as political parties (Doell et al., 2021), and have their political attitudes influenced as a result of overriding in-group pressures (Mason, 2018; Pierson & Schickler, 2020).

Drawing from social identity theory and self-categorization theory (Tajfel et al., 1971), social psychologists have provided similar explanations for the motivation behind individuals adopting attitudes aligned with their social groups or parties. Theories such as the social identity model of pro-environmental action (Fritzsche et al., 2018) and the theory of identity-based motivation (Oyserman, 2009) suggest that individuals are motivated to monitor their beliefs and attitudes to maintain a sense of belonging to a group. This translates to a conscious in-group social pressure (e.g., Cole et al., 2022; Goldberg et al., 2020; Rinscheid et al., 2021) that drives partisans towards a group-based polarization (Cole et al., 2023). Simultaneously, drawing mainly on ideology but also on identity, politically motivated reasoning operates unconsciously as partisans will instinctively tend to interpret information and form beliefs in a manner that aligns with their pre-existing political beliefs or affiliations, rather than purely based on objective evidence or logic (Kunda, 1990; Stanovich, 2021).

As individuals actively seek to sort themselves into groups and judge others based on group memberships (Mackie, 1986), we can assume that there is a deliberative

component—i.e., one involving conscious mental effort—to the group-level polarization fueled by in-group social pressure. At the same time, politically motivated reasoning adds an instinctive—and, possibly, affective (Zajonc, 1980)—polarization that draws on ideology and identity to shape the unconscious attitudes of the U.S. public (Iyengar et al., 2019; Iyengar & Westwood, 2015). Therefore, we predict that the influence of political orientation on explicit (i.e., conscious) attitudes about wind farms is stronger than on implicit (i.e., unconscious) attitudes because we assume that in-group social pressure mainly operates at an explicit level while politically motivated reasoning can be present at both implicit and explicit levels. By comparing implicit and explicit attitudes, we will assess the extent to which in-group pressure amplifies political polarization, as a separate contribution from the differences already present at the implicit level.

H1: Political orientation predicts (a) implicit attitudes and (b) explicit attitudes about local wind farms.

H2: The effect of political orientation on explicit attitudes is stronger than on implicit attitudes.

In the context of forming attitudes about a local wind farm, we assume that the polarizing effect of in-group pressure is dependent on the strength of perceived within-party support—because research shows that in-group social norms shape climate change-related views and policy support (Cialdini & Jacobson, 2021; Dixon et al., 2024; Fielding et al., 2020). Moreover, Van Boven et al. (2018) found that partisans overestimate how much other Democrats and Republicans are swayed by partisanship, and concluded that this foments false norms of partisan opposition that, in turn, influence people’s personal policy support. These findings, coupled with the fact that normative information from people with similar social identities is more powerful than normative information from

people with different social identities (Abrams et al., 1990), helps to explain the role of perceptions of social norms in fueling in-group pressures.

Social norms are thus determinant, but they are also malleable. Cole et al. (2023) see in this malleability an opportunity to alleviate the norm-based polarization caused by in-group pressures. They suggest leveraging perceptions of in-group social norms to depolarize attitudes: experimental evidence shows that if survey participants are given information that corrects their perceptions of within-party support for a climate policy, partisans seem to adjust their corresponding attitudes accordingly (Cole et al., 2022; Macy et al., 2019).

Similarly, we expect to find that the effect of political orientation on attitudes towards having wind farms nearby will depend on the level of perceived support within one's political party. This perceived within-party support is subjective and depends—among other factors not measured in this study—on people's perception of descriptive norms, that is, the rules they believe they must follow because it is what the majority in their party would do (Cole et al., 2022). Therefore, when within-party descriptive norms are clear, partisans may feel pressured not to deviate from the majority's opinion in order to still be considered as part of the in-group.

Specifically, we predict that attitudes will improve and converge as perceived within-party support increases (i.e., become more positive and similar across the political spectrum, for Democrats and Republicans alike). First, when perceived within-party support for wind farms is low, partisans should express a negative attitude against windfarms. Conversely, when perceptions of within-party support increase but remain uncertain, we expect that political attitudes will not differ much between participants with different political orientations. This is due to the ambiguity surrounding party support, which leads individuals to adopt a more cautious stance. Such behavior is consistent with

group-based polarization because partisans are expected to align their opinions with their political identity to maintain their sense of belonging within the party. Consequently, those perceiving a high within-party support are expected to report more positive views on wind farms. This hypothesis is summarized as follows:

H3: The influence of political orientation on (a) implicit and (b) explicit attitudes towards local wind farms is contingent on the level of perceived within-party support, with attitudes positively converging (i.e., becoming more positive and similar across the political spectrum) as perceived within-party support increases.

At the explicit level, even for partisans who perceive high within-party support, we anticipate differences in attitudes across party lines, with Democrats likely expressing more positive attitudes than Republicans. These remaining differences in attitudes about wind farms are expected to be issue-based because norm-based polarization should not be active when perceived within-party support is high. In the next section we hypothesize about the extent to which issue-framing can bridge the remaining ideological partisan gap.

2.3. Framing as a depolarizing intervention

According to Cole et al.'s (2023) guidelines for developing interventions to depolarize climate-related attitudes, frames emphasizing the risks of climate change in ways that appeal to political partisans—i.e., by highlighting issues aligned with their political interests—should alleviate individual-level, issue-based polarization. However, the effectiveness of this type of framing has been found to be limited in previous studies (e.g., Singh & Swanson, 2017; Wolsko et al., 2016). This ineffectiveness can be observed both when framings targeting Democrats merely serve to confirm pre-existing opinions without causing an attitude shift, or when messages are specifically tailored for

Republicans without building trust, which often results in backlash or reactance (e.g., Marcos et al., 2023; Zhou, 2016).

The cumulative evidence in the political polarization literature suggests that the effect of framings is, at best, small to medium, but frequently negligible (Amsalem & Zoizner, 2022; Li & Su, 2018; Rode et al., 2021). However, we posit that an opportunity for effectively using framing arises when partisans perceive a high level of within-party support. In such situations, framing strategies may become viable without the risk of backlash from Republicans because group norm-based polarization is less likely to be active. This implies that individuals might be influenced by framings which emphasize issues relevant to their political ideologies without encountering cognitive resistance (Cole et al., 2023). The tailoring of the frame is crucial to overcome the bias caused by politically motivated reasoning (Slothuus & de Vreese, 2010), which prevents any message from influencing people unless it aligns with their pre-existing political beliefs (Kunda, 1990).

To design these depolarizing frames, Cole et al. (2023)—see also Richter (2014)—propose tapping into various issues that appeal to both liberals and conservatives, responding to threats to their worldviews. In the context of the energy transition, Democrats may find a climate disaster risk convincing due to their belief in climate change and stronger support for climate change mitigation compared to Republicans and conservatives in general (Doell et al., 2021; Van Boven et al., 2018). In contrast, refraining from mentioning climate change and framing the slowing down of the energy transition as an energy security threat can boost Republicans' support (Feldman & Hart, 2018; Fielding et al., 2020), particularly when underscoring the issue of energy dependence (Gainous & Merry, 2022). Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H4: When perceived within-party support for wind farms is high (i.e., group norm-based polarization is not active for Democrats and Republicans), (a) climate disaster risk framings significantly increase positive attitudes towards wind farms for Democrats but not for Republicans, while (b) energy security framings increase positive attitudes towards wind farms for Republicans but not for Democrats.

3. Methods

3.1. Participants and procedure

We recruited a politically balanced random sample of 1300 participants (650 Democrats and 650 Republicans) from a Prolific online panel of the U.S. population (49.80% female, 49.60% male, 0.6% other, $M_{\text{age}} = 45.65$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 13.83$). The demographic characteristics of the sample are detailed in the Appendix (Table A.1). The final sample consisted of 1,240 participants as 60 participants were excluded either for not completing the survey (13), failing attention checks (6), responding inconsistently (4), or failing to complete the IAT as instructed (37). We collected the sample evenly from only two political groups because the U.S. political system is predominantly a two-party system, dominated almost entirely by the Republicans and Democrats, with third parties rarely winning seats in Congress or state legislatures. That is, half of the study participants were individuals who indicated their political affiliation as Democrats on the Prolific survey platform, while the other half indicated their affiliation as Republicans. Although participants' political affiliation was already available from metadata provided by Prolific, we measured on a 5-point Likert scale the extent to which participants considered themselves Conservatives and Liberals. The responses to these questions, ranging from very conservative to very liberal, were coded and then matched with participants' metadata to create a four-level categorical variable for political orientation (Very liberal Democrat, Moderate Democrat, Moderate Republican and Very conservative Republican)—see Appendix.

Participants were randomly assigned to one of six experimental factor treatments of a 2 (implicit attitude test vs. explicit questionnaire) \times 3 (control vs. climate disaster risk framing vs. energy security risk framing) between-subjects factorial design. Participants in both the implicit and explicit attitudes groups read a brief text describing the increasing relevance of wind energy as a renewable resource. Thereafter, they were asked to imagine that they just learned about a new wind farm development being planned near their home. Those participants who were assigned to the control group were presented only with this scenario.

Participants sorted into the two framing groups were provided additional information about the wind farm development respective to their frames. Those exposed to the climate disaster risk frame were informed about extreme weather events and environmental degradation and about the ways in which wind energy could help mitigate climate change. Participants in the energy security risk frame condition received information about the United States' economic reliance on oil and gas from other countries and were then informed that wind energy could safeguard national energy independence and security. Exact wording of the frames and manipulation checks are provided in the Appendix.

After each group read their respective prompt, participants were randomly assigned to one of two tasks: a questionnaire or an Implicit Association Test (IAT). The questionnaire assessed explicit political attitudes, while the IAT assessed implicit attitudes about wind farms. The use of the IAT allows us to measure how strongly participants associate various concepts with attributes or stereotypes, thereby uncovering their unconscious biases (Greenwald et al., 1998).

For administering the IAT, we used the JavaScript-based IAT for Qualtrics developed by Carpenter et al. (2019). Participants taking the IAT were instructed to place their hands on the keyboard and to complete seven blocks of stimuli sorting trials. In each trial, a

word showing an attribute (e.g., “Awful”) or a concept (e.g., “Wind turbine”) was displayed on the screen. Participants were instructed to categorize the stimuli as fast as they could by pressing an assigned keyboard key with the corresponding hand (e.g., left for “wind farm” or “positive,” right for “gas-fired power plant” or “negative”). In subsequent blocks, the assignments would be reversed (e.g., left for “gas-fired power plant” or “positive,” right for “wind farm” or “negative”). The reason for this reversal is to measure the time it takes for an individual to categorize wind farms when shown together with positive and negative attributes. The underlying logic is that participants would have to make more effort to override their existing mental associations when concepts and attributes were presented in a reversed manner. This extra effort would slow down their responses if, for example, they associate wind farms with positive attributes but, in a given block, must use the same key for both wind farms and negative attributes. The speed at which each participant sorts stimuli in one block compared to the sorting speed of the same participant in other blocks reveals its implicit bias (Lane et al., 2007), as individuals can categorize stimuli more quickly when the pairings align with their unconscious beliefs (Greenwald et al., 1998). This sorting tasks were designed to reveal whether there was a stronger association of wind farms with positive attributes compared to negative attributes. Participants underwent the procedure seven times (i.e., seven blocks), each time switching attributes and concepts. Three blocks included 20 practice trials to familiarize participants with the stimuli and sorting process, while the remaining blocks were divided into a 20-trial practice part and a 40-trial critical part from which the final implicit association measurement was derived.

The study design was pre-registered on AsPredicted (https://aspredicted.org/ZX9_17B). The materials, pre-registration, data and code for this study are available as an Open

Science Framework (OSF) permanent archive at:
https://osf.io/6y3hs/?view_only=a8125c7c1f734cf0a9b06f36c8dcda35.

3.2. Measures

The IAT assigned participants tasks designed to implicitly measure their unconscious associations about wind farms. The resulting implicit bias is a relative measure of the strength of the association between two contrasted concepts and two contrasted attributes. As opposed to wind farms, the concept of gas-fired power plant was presented but its sole purpose was to serve as a benchmark to compare the relative positive attitudes about wind farms with that of a business-as-usual equivalent. This approach is similar to Firestone and Kirk’s (2019), who asked U.S. participants whether they prefer living near a wind project relative to a centralized power plant sited a similar distance. We decided to use five different wordings per concept and attribute. This choice aligns with the commonly recommended range of four to six different stimuli (Greenwald et al., 1998; Pogacar et al., 2019). The stimuli used in the IAT is presented in Table 2.

Concepts	Stimuli
Nearby windfarm	<i>Wind park, Wind turbine, Windmill, Green energy, Renewable energy</i>
Nearby gas-fired power plant	<i>Power plant, Gas plant, Gas pipeline, Fossil fuel, Carbon emissions</i>
Attributes	Stimuli
Positive	<i>Cheerful, Excellent, Good, Happy, Pleasant</i>
Negative	<i>Angry, Awful, Bad, Disgust, Hateful</i>

Table 2. Concepts and attributes shown to participants in the IAT.

As an implicit attitude measure, a D-score (i.e., a standardized discrepancy score) was computed for each participant based on their sorting speed of words in each block (Greenwald et al., 2003). Positive D-scores mean implicit positive attitudes about wind farms in comparison to conventional gas-fired power plants, while negative D-scores indicated an unconscious negative attitude about wind farms. In our analysis, we refer to

the average D-score as mean implicit attitudes (M_i). The reliability of this implicit attitudes measure was established with a satisfactory alpha coefficient ($\alpha = 0.87$), as determined through the split-half procedure method (De Houwer & De Bruycker, 2007). Less than 0.001% of trials were excluded due to slow responses (i.e., reaction times exceeding 10 seconds). 37 participants—5.52% of the sample—were excluded for excessively fast responses (i.e., reaction times below 300 milliseconds). Given that participants were instructed to press the keys as fast as possible, the observed error rate of 7.69% during the stimuli sorting process was deemed acceptable, in accordance with established standards (Rudman, 2011).

As for explicit attitudes, participants were asked about their opinion regarding a hypothetical wind farm project situated near their residence. Employing a three-item scale with 5-point semantic anchors ranging from *feeling very bad* = 1 to *feeling very good* = 5, *do not like it at all* = 1 to *like it very much* = 5, and *very negative* = 1 to *very positive* = 5, participants conveyed their explicit attitudes. A reliability analysis confirmed this three-item explicit attitude scale had a high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.98$). Perception of within-party support for wind energy expansion was measured using a 5-point Likert scale (“*How widely held do you think this opinion is among Republicans/Democrats?*”) and was then collapsed to a three-level categorical variable (low, unsure, high) to ease analysis and reporting—see Appendix. Despite not being used for hypothesis testing, we also measured beliefs and intentions to see how they correlated with the explicit attitude measure used in the study, and to explore whether polarization was equally strong for beliefs, attitudes and intentions—these additional constructs and analyses are reported in the Appendix. Lastly, all participants answered demographic questions.

Parallel to the notation for D-scores derived from the IAT (M_i), we designate the mean explicit attitudes as M_e . The political partisan gap at the explicit level is represented by

the difference $\Delta M_e = M_{e,dem} - M_{e,rep}$, where $M_{e,dem}$ signifies mean explicit attitudes among Democrats, and $M_{e,rep}$ represents the mean explicit attitudes among Republicans. The same applies for the implicit level ($\Delta M_i = M_{i,dem} - M_{i,rep}$).

4. Results

4.1. *Explicit and implicit attitudes*

To confirm that explicit attitudes were more polarized than implicit ones, we first ensured that $\Delta M_e > \Delta M_i$, and that the effect size of ΔM_e was significantly larger than the effect size of ΔM_i . The latter was done with a Z-test comparing the two Cohen's ds (1988) obtained from the t-tests with the implicit and explicit measures (Borenstein et al., 2009).

At the implicit level, unconscious attitudes towards wind farms were more positive for Democrats ($M_{i,Dem} = 0.65$, $SD_{i,Dem} = 0.41$) than for Republicans ($M_{i,Rep} = 0.53$, $SD_{i,Rep} = 0.46$; $\Delta M_i = 0.12$, 95% CI (0.04, 0.18), $t(636) = 3.23$, $P = 0.001$, $d = 0.26$), providing support for H1a (Figure 1a). This significant partisan gap was created by very conservative Republicans, whose implicit attitudes towards wind farms were significantly lower than moderate Republicans' ($M_{i,Conservative Rep} = 0.48$, $SD_{i,Conservative Rep} = 0.45$, vs. $M_{i,Moderate Rep} = 0.60$, $SD_{i,Moderate Rep} = 0.46$, $t(315) = 2.43$, $P = 0.016$). Notably, there were no significant differences between moderate Republicans' and Democrats' attitudes (Figure 1b). That is, moderate Republicans' implicit attitudes were closer to Democrats' attitudes than to very conservative Republicans' attitudes.

However, the distance between moderate Republicans' attitudes increased relative to moderate Democrats' when participants consciously reported their opinion about having wind farms nearby (Figure 1d). Overall, the explicit attitude towards wind farms was more positive for Democrats ($M_{e,Dem} = 4.24$, $SD_{e,Dem} = 0.90$) than for Republicans ($M_{e,Rep} = 2.95$, $SD_{e,Rep} = 1.40$; $\Delta M_e = 1.29$, 95% CI (1.10, 1.48), $t(600) = 13.35$, $P < 0.001$, $d =$

1.09), providing support for H1b (Figure 1c). Although moderate Republicans' attitudes were significantly different from moderate Democrats' at the explicit level ($t(224) = 6.03$, $P < 0.001$), a significant difference remained between moderate Republicans' and very conservative Republicans' attitudes ($M_{e,Conservative Rep} = 2.73$, $SD_{e,Conservative Rep} = 1.48$, vs. $M_{e,Moderate Rep} = 3.26$, $SD_{e,Moderate Rep} = 1.23$, $t(301) = 3.32$, $P = 0.001$).

Fig. 1. Mean values for implicit and explicit attitudes towards wind farms, by political orientation.

The partisan gap more than doubled at the explicit level ($\Delta M_e = 1.29$, $d = 1.09$), relative to its size at the implicit level ($\Delta M_i = 0.12$, $d = 0.26$): the significant difference in effect

sizes ($Z = 7.03$, $P < 0.001$) showed that consciously reported explicit attitudes were more polarized than the unconscious—implicit—ones, providing support for H2.

4.2. The polarizing effect of in-group social pressure

A two-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effects of political orientation and perceived within-party support on implicit and explicit attitudes toward wind farms. There was a statistically significant interaction between political orientation and perceived within party support, which predicted attitudes toward wind farms at the implicit level ($F(6, 626) = 2.985$, $P = 0.007$) and at the explicit level ($F(6, 590) = 2.883$, $P = 0.009$). Table 3 summarizes the simple main effects for every level of perceived within-party support.

Attitude towards having a wind farm nearby	Perceived within-party support	Political orientation				<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
		Very liberal Democrat	Moderate Democrat	Moderate Republican	Very conservative Republican		
Implicit (IAT)	Low	0.25 (-0.24, 0.73)	0.46 (0.14, 0.78)	0.58 (0.48, 0.68)	0.50 (0.41, 0.58)	0.42	0.423
	Unsure	0.36 (0.15, 0.57)	0.69 (0.42, 0.96)	0.65 (0.53, 0.78)	0.57 (0.43, 0.71)	2.05	0.106
	High	0.66 (0.60, 0.72)	0.68 (0.60, 0.77)	0.58 (0.43, 0.73)	0.34 (0.21, 0.48)	6.85	<0.001
Explicit (Reported)	Low	5.00 (2.92, 7.08)	3.89 (2.69, 5.01)	2.87 (2.62, 3.13)	1.93 (1.70, 2.15)	14.04	<0.001
	Unsure	3.58 (3.04, 4.12)	3.55 (2.92, 4.17)	3.55 (3.22, 3.89)	3.16 (2.85, 3.47)	1.27	0.285
	High	4.33 (4.18, 4.48)	4.26 (4.03, 4.49)	3.88 (3.45, 4.30)	3.82 (3.51, 4.13)	3.65	0.013

Note. 95% confidence intervals are reported in parenthesis.

Table 3. Estimated mean implicit and explicit attitudes towards having a wind farm nearby, by perceived within-party support and political orientation.

There was no significant impact on implicit attitudes when perceived within-party support was low, and it only had an effect when this perception was high. The moderating effect of within-party support on implicit attitudes was only significant for very liberal Democrats ($F(2, 626) = 4.841$, $P = 0.008$), and it did not significantly alter the attitudes

for the rest of the political spectrum. Since the increase of perceived within-party support did not lead to a convergence in implicit attitudes across the political spectrum (See Figure A.1 in the Appendix), H3a could not be supported.

However, at the explicit level, both high and low awareness of within-party support for wind farms significantly influenced explicit attitudes across the political spectrum (Table 3). The moderation reduced the partisan gap as perceived within party support increased, thus providing support for H3b. As shown in Figure 2, partisans' explicit attitudes diverged strongly when perceived within party support was low. This divergence was primarily due to Republicans aligning with their party's stance, while a few Democratic outliers (hence the large confidence intervals) considered that their party was not supportive of wind farms and expressed very positive attitudes towards wind farms themselves. These differences converged when perceived within party support perception was high. The hypothesized attitude convergence related to an increase in perceived within party support—which we attributed to in-group social pressure—had an effect across the political spectrum: The moderating effect of within-party support perception on explicit attitudes was significant for very liberal Democrats ($F(2, 590) = 3.724, P = 0.025$), moderate Republicans ($F(2, 590) = 9.867, P < 0.001$) and very conservative Republicans ($F(2, 590) = 51.985, P < 0.001$), but it was not significant for moderate Democrats ($F(2, 590) = 2.303, P = 0.101$).

Fig. 2. Estimated marginal means of explicit attitudes towards wind farms, by political orientation and perceived within party support.

Despite high within-party support leading to positive and convergent attitudes across the political spectrum, there were still significant differences between Democrats ($M_{e, Dem} = 4.30$, $SD_{e, Dem} = 0.84$) and Republicans ($M_{e, Rep} = 3.84$, $SD_{e, Rep} = 1.23$; $\Delta M_e = 0.47$, 95% CI (0.22, 0.72), $t(336) = 3.69$, $P < 0.001$). This shows that the partisan gap observed at the explicit level decreased but that a significant gap remains, which is not attributable to group norm-based polarization, because in-group social pressure to oppose wind farms should not be present when perceived within-party support is high. The next section explores the extent to which framings can bridge the partisan gap that still remains in this case.

4.3. The role of framing in changing explicit attitudes

A three-way ANOVA revealed there was a statistically significant three-way interaction between political orientation, perceived within-party support and framing, $F(9, 569) = 2.796$, $P = 0.003$. There was a statistically significant simple two-way interaction between

perceived within party support and framing for very conservative Republicans ($F(4, 569) = 4.902, P = 0.001$), but the interaction was not significant for moderate Republicans nor for moderate and strong Democrats.

There were statistically significant simple main effects of framing for very conservative Republicans who were unsure about the shared perceptions within their party ($F(2, 569) = 6.568, P = 0.002$) and for those who were sure about other Republicans' positive stance ($F(2, 569) = 3.286, P = 0.038$). As expected, the effect of framing was not significant when very conservative Republicans perceived that within-party support for wind farms was low ($F(2, 569) = 1.073, P = 0.343$). When very conservative Republicans were unsure about the shared perceptions within their party, the energy security risk framing reduced explicit attitudes about wind farms relative to the control group ($\Delta = -1.31, 95\% \text{ CI } (-2.12, -0.50), F(2, 569) = 6.568, P = 0.002$), whereas the perception of high within-party support turned the effect of the energy security risk framing positive and significant ($\Delta = 0.98, 95\% \text{ CI } (0.22, 1.75), F(2, 569) = 3.606, P = 0.012$). Therefore, framings that highlight energy security risk can increase very conservative Republicans' attitudes towards wind farms, but only when they perceived that within-party support is high. If the same framing is used when within party support is low or unsure (i.e., when group-norm based polarization can be present), there may be a backlash and the energy security framing will negatively affect very conservative Republicans' attitudes. Figure 3 summarises the effects of framings across the political spectrum and for different levels of perceived within party support, showing that the climate disaster risk framing was not effective — rejecting H4a—, and that the energy security framing was only effective in the specific case of very conservative Republicans who perceived high within party support—partially supporting H4b.

Note. (*) indicates significant effects of framing. Pairwise comparisons for Democrats were not estimable when perceived within-party support was low because there were few observations in this subgroup.

Fig. 3. Pairwise comparisons of the effect of climate disaster risk and energy security risk framings, segmented by political orientation and perceived within-party support.

5. Discussion

Our results show that explicit attitudes about wind farms are more polarized than implicit ones, thus supporting the notion that more polarizing processes operate when participants form their attitudes after a more deliberative elaboration process. The observed limited effectiveness of framing and the more substantial influence of within-party support perceptions in our study align with Cole et al.'s (2023) recommendation that interventions targeting group-level processes may be more effective than those focusing on individual-level processes. Previous research has highlighted the dominance of group norms-based polarization over ideology-based polarization when it comes to promoting pro-environmental behavior in general (Masson & Fritsche, 2021), and our results point to a similar pattern in the context of polarized attitudes toward local wind farms.

In line with the literature on ideologically targeted messaging trying to influence attitudes about renewable energy (e.g., Aklin & Urpelainen, 2013), we obtained mixed results concerning the role of framing. Our findings show that while frames incorporating partisan concerns are supposed to be more persuasive to gain support for solar and wind energy (e.g., Gustafson et al., 2022), tailored frames that emphasize the risks of delaying the energy transition were only partially effective in the context of nearby wind farms. When in-group social pressure to oppose wind farms is absent (i.e., when there is high perceived within-party support), energy security risk framings are effective for very conservative Republicans but have limited impact on moderate Republicans. Democrats, however, remain unaffected by climate disaster risk framings. This limited impact of framing aligns with extant research (Buchanan et al., 2022; Marcos et al., 2023; Singh & Swanson, 2017), which highlights the impracticality of relying on tailored messages to effectively depolarize partisans' climate-related attitudes.

The absence of significant changes in Democrats' attitudes following exposure to the climate disaster risk framing could be attributed to their familiarity with the frame. Democratic politicians primarily present the transition to renewable energy as a critical strategy for mitigating climate change. Although we have not measured participants' familiarity with the frames, Democrats' lack of significant shift in attitudes after reading the climate risk frame is consistent with their already strong support for climate action and prior exposure to climate change mitigation narratives—suggesting that the impact of such narratives has already been factored into their attitudes when we measured them. Moreover, Democrats' reactions to the energy security frame were not significantly different from their reactions to the climate disaster frame, as both elicited positive but non-significant effects. Therefore, the energy security frame could be considered somewhat bipartisan, as it appears to foster positive attitudes without causing backlash among Democrats and addresses an issue relevant to both parties.

In contrast, our findings concerning Republicans require closer examination due to the intriguing result that attitudes about wind farms were more favorable among moderate Republicans, whereas the effect of framing was more pronounced among very conservative Republicans. A demographic analysis of our sample revealed that the very conservative Republican cohort skewed significantly older compared to the moderate Republican group. This age difference may partially explain the more positive attitudes among moderate Republicans, as nationwide surveys indicate that younger Republicans are more inclined to support wind energy projects (Kennedy et al., 2023). Furthermore, the greater receptivity of older, more conservative Republicans to the energy security framing may stem from their lived experiences, particularly their familiarity with and concern over energy security issues, potentially influenced by the oil shocks of the 1970s.

In contrast, younger moderate Republicans may not share these same concerns or experiences.

Recent research shows that 80–90% of Americans underestimate the prevalence of support for major climate change mitigation policies (Sparkman et al., 2022), and that this misperception of in-group support for climate action is primarily observed among Republicans who are already opposed to such actions (Dixon et al., 2024). Our results showing that participants who perceived high within-party support had a positive response to the energy security framing, whereas those uncertain about within-party support exhibited a negative response, back up the notion that the inability to recognize high within-party support may be correlated with pre-existing opposition to climate action. Moreover, the energy security framings may elicit backlash, as evidenced by the response of uncertain Republicans in this study, not only due to in-group social pressure but also because the survey context may lack the necessary trust-building elements—the lack of which tends to result in psychological reactance (e.g., Marcos et al., 2023; Song et al., 2018).

The shift in explicit attitudes among Republicans based on their perceived within-party support is a noteworthy result that mirrors ongoing trends and underscores the disruptive nature of social dynamics: across the US, organized opposition groups, historically affiliated with local fossil fuel interests, consistently impede the siting and development of wind energy projects (Crawford et al., 2022; Fergen et al., 2021), often through the disproportionate amplification of wind farm opponents' voices. This phenomenon has been characterized as a “democratic deficit” by Bell et al. (2005, 2013), wherein “a majority support wind energy developments but a minority stop them” (Bell et al., 2005, p. 466). In a democratic deficit context, local decision-makers tend to hear predominantly from wind farm opponents at government meetings, online or via personal

communication, but not supporters, despite the latter's greater number, leading to an overestimation of opposition sentiment—and thus a perceived lack of within-party support. Our findings showing the important role of perceived within-party support suggest this playbook is effective, and also align with Dixon et al.'s (2024) conclusion that Republicans may be discouraged from expressing their support to wind farm expansion because there is an overrepresentation of minority viewpoints (i.e., Party elites or very conservative Republicans who strongly oppose climate action) in their information environment. To address this issue, communication strategies beyond framing (which has proven ineffective in most cases in this study) can be employed to correct misperceptions of in-group social norms. Other potential depolarizing interventions include designing communication campaigns that leverage superordinate identities, feature trusted leaders, and convey bipartisan support for potential solutions (Cole et al., 2022). Additionally, it is essential to acknowledge that the energy transition involves tradeoffs and will likely produce both “winners” and “losers” (Newell et al., 2022). Policymakers must address these tradeoffs, and communication campaigns must effectively convey this complexity.

Our results suggest that while framing messages to align with partisan norms is likely still important, it may not be as important as using depolarizing communication and messengers speaking in venues that accurately reflect or at least work against misrepresenting higher levels of within-party support. For instance, for Republicans, framing the trade-offs of wind energy around partisan issues such as strong property rights, restrictive zoning as government overreach, wind energy as farmland preservation, or national energy security—as tested here—is important. But so is demonstrating within-party support by relying on locally respected, conservative groups or individuals, such as other farmers with wind-turbine leases, University Extension personnel, or conservative

advocacy groups to deliver those messages and participate in meaningful, respectful and deliberative community listening sessions or decision-making processes.

6. Limitations and further research

Our study showed the dampening of group-based polarization as perceived within-party support increased, but we did not manipulate those perceptions. Rather, we relied on self-reported perceptions to segment participants by groups. Therefore, we refrain from deriving further conclusions about the efficacy of influencing in-group social norms to depolarize attitudes, particularly considering the inherent difficulty in influencing conservatives' perceptions in this regard—as conservatives actively seek to preserve the existing within-group consensus (Jost et al., 2018).

We also refrain from generalizing our findings related to onshore wind farms to offshore wind farms. Although the perceived distance might be greater for offshore wind farms (Haggett, 2008), this does not render them less controversial (Devine-Wright & Howes, 2010), as place attachment appears to significantly influence coastal residents' attitudes towards offshore wind farms (Firestone, Bidwell, et al., 2018; Gonyo et al., 2021). Consequently, we cannot extend our findings to offshore wind farms because we did not measure key variables such as place attachment. This remains an important area for future research, especially given the rapid expansion of the offshore wind industry in the United States (Musial et al., 2023).

While our focus was on influencing issue-based polarization through framing, future research could explore interventions leveraging partisan identification too to directly tackle group norm-based polarization, as suggested by prior literature (Fritsche et al., 2018; Masson & Fritsche, 2021; Pearson et al., 2016). To the best of our knowledge, no

study has simultaneously tested interventions addressing issue-based and group norm-based polarization regarding attitudes about renewable energy.

We used a framing intervention primarily aimed at influencing issue-based polarization, without making specific predictions regarding its emotional component known as affective polarization (Iyengar et al., 2012, 2019), which may differ from or coincide with the effect of politically motivated reasoning—in some contexts, affective polarization can increase while ideological divisions shrink (Levendusky & Malhotra, 2016a, 2016b). Therefore, future research aimed at bridging issue-based polarization should also consider this emotional component, which partisan sorting and message frames alone might not adequately solve (Törnberg, 2022). Given the difficulty of this task, many researchers suggest a more direct depolarizing strategy, focusing on correcting misperceptions not about specific issues like the benefits of wind farms but rather about out-party composition (i.e., individuals frequently overestimate how well those who support a party conform to party-stereotypical traits), as these biased beliefs are linked to partisan affect, beliefs about out-party extremity, and allegiance to one's own party (Ahler & Sood, 2018; Hartman et al., 2022).

Our findings prompt speculation about the influence of group-level, norm-based polarization, as we observed a significant moderating effect of perceived within-party support. However, we did not directly measure group-level polarization. Future studies could use innovative methodologies such as the Cluster-Polarization Coefficient (Mehlhoff, 2023) and the Equal Size Binary Grouping Technique (Tang et al., 2022) to gain deeper insights into and confirm changes in group-level polarization toward renewable energy development. Moreover, our analysis of in-group social pressure was based on a measurement of descriptive norms. We did not measure injunctive norms, which could have implications for understanding the mechanisms driving group-level

polarization. It is crucial for future research measuring group-level polarization to explore whether changes in perceived within-party support depend on descriptive norms, injunctive norms, or both, as these perceptions are often intertwined (Cialdini et al., 1990).

We did not collect data based on the geographical distribution of the sample. Although the sample was politically balanced and diverse in terms of education, income, and age, we acknowledge that it is not fully representative, as it does not include a balanced proportion of participants from all U.S. states.

7. Conclusion and policy implications

Political polarization hinders consensus-building and effective communication around wind energy development, particularly for individuals living near wind farms or considering wind farm proposals. Addressing this challenge requires depolarizing communication strategies, but pinpointing where to concentrate efforts requires disentangling the effects of unconscious issue-based and conscious group norm-based polarization processes. Our findings underscore the pronounced polarization of explicit attitudes toward wind farms compared to implicit attitudes, highlighting the influential role of conscious group-level processes in shaping explicit attitudes toward wind farms. Overall, framing does not significantly impact explicit attitudes, with one notable exception: energy security frames can be effective in improving explicit attitudes among politically conservative audiences. We conclude that issue-framing alone is not a sufficiently powerful strategy to consistently alter individuals' positions on nearby wind farms.

The significant impact of perceptions of within-party support on explicit attitudes emphasizes the importance of addressing group norm-based polarization. Since the issue-

framing interventions tested in the present study yielded inconclusive results regarding issue-based polarization, interventions targeting group-level processes may be more effective. Some key strategies for depolarizing group-level processes have already been identified in the literature: communications correcting misperceptions of in-group social norms, leveraging superordinate identities, featuring trusted leaders and conveying bipartisan support from the general public or elites for potential solutions (Cole et al., 2023). In terms of policy implications, our results stress the need to consider both issue-based and group norm-based polarization—but with a special emphasis on the latter—when designing communication strategies to garner local support for wind farm development.

Given the prominence of group norm-based polarization in our findings, managing perceptions of in-group social pressure emerges as a vital strategy. We contend that bridging the attitude gap hinges on addressing group norm-based polarization first by rectifying misconceptions of within-party social norms. For example, Cole et al. (2022) found that participants' perceptions of their political ingroup's social norms regarding climate policy prioritization were the most robust predictor of climate policy support. In the same study, they experimentally manipulated the information provided about Democrats' and Republicans' descriptive norms, demonstrating that simply presenting this information can influence perceptions of their political ingroup's social norms and thus effectively impact policy support.

To effectively address group-level processes that contribute to polarization, it is crucial not only to correct misconceptions about within-party support but also to ensure that social identities and affective polarization (i.e., positive feelings toward one's own group and negative feelings toward the outgroup) do not pose obstacles. Regarding social identities, messages that prime political identities may exacerbate partisan divides on

climate issues (Guilbeault et al., 2018). Therefore, leveraging nonpoliticized identities that transcend partisan affiliations can improve climate change attitudes (Cole et al., 2023). For instance, framing climate change as a moral or religious issue (Goldberg et al., 2019), priming parental identity (Diamond, 2020), or emphasizing global identity (McFarland et al., 2019) has been shown to increase pro-environmental attitudes. Lastly, when it comes to affective polarization, overcoming the distrust and negative feelings towards messages perceived as originating from the outgroup requires communication strategies that involve experts and bipartisan groups (Flores et al., 2022), convey scientific consensus (Linden et al., 2018), and utilize trusted leaders from both Democratic and Republican backgrounds to address their respective audiences (Benegal & Scruggs, 2018).

Despite our conclusion on the predominant role of group-level processes, individual-level processes also merit consideration. While issue-framing was not effective in our study, the literature identifies solution aversion as another polarizing factor at the individual-level (Cole et al., 2023), which framing might help address. Solution aversion is the psychological denial of a problem due to the dislike of its potential solutions (Campbell & Kay, 2014). This concept helps explain why conservatives may be skeptical about the renewable energy transition, as they often oppose the kind of big government interventions that are necessary to mitigate climate change. Therefore, to reduce Republicans' skepticism towards wind farms, presenting the energy transition as driven by the private sector might be effective.

Although in this study we have dismissed issue-framing as a tool for depolarizing attitudes towards local wind farms, it may still hold value. Frames could help address other individual-level processes like solution aversion, especially if communicated by trusted leaders in a bipartisan manner. This combination of strategies—addressing

individual-level processes through framing to counter solution aversion, and group-level processes by using trusted leaders, emphasizing superordinate identities, and conveying bipartisan support—warrants further exploration. This approach seems promising for effectively choosing the right message—and the right messenger—to increase perceptions of within-party support, which we identified as crucial in shaping attitudes towards local wind farms.

8. References

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